

Church of the Panagia, Kapetaniana (Monofatsi), Crete

By Nicolyna Enriquez, University of California, Los Angeles

Entry tags: Religious Group, Byzantine, Church, Church, Greek, Byzantine, Religious Place, Language, Medieval Christianity, Monument, Orthodoxy

The church of the Panagia, located in the village of Kapetaniana on the southern coast of Crete is located ten kilometers inland at an altitude of eight hundred meters. It surveys the Libyan Sea to the south and Mount Kofinas, the highest peak of the Asterousia mountain range, to the east. Dated by inscription to the Byzantine year 6910 (1401-2) the vaulted nave of the church is divided into two bays by a transverse arch. A narthex, whose pointed barrel vault is higher than that of the nave, is positioned on the western side of the building and is connected to the nave by means of an archway. The wall paintings in both the church and narthex are generally well preserved and include one of the most extensive cycles of the Life of the Virgin in Byzantine art. The inclusion of a large number of holy monks in the decorative program indicate that the church functioned as a *katholikon*, the main church of a monastery. Indeed, the church once belonged to the now destroyed Monastery of Vathmou (later the Monastery of the Panagia of Kyrie Eleison). This function is also confirmed by the dedicatory inscription which names the "hieromonachos (ordained monk) and spiritual father, the priest Grigorios Kalamaras" as the church's sponsor. The wall paintings of the sanctuary include the Virgin and Child in the half dome of the apse flanked by two angels in medallions. Below this image are four co-officiating bishops flanking the Melismos. Above the sanctuary, on the triumphal arch, is the image of God as the Ancient of Days flanked by the four Evangelists. Below this image is the Annunciation, although only the Archangel Gabriel can still be distinguished today. Inside the conch of the prothesis niche (on the left side of the apse) is the image of Christ as the Man of Sorrow. Above the niche is the deacon St. Stephen. Two bishop saints are located along the northern wall of the sanctuary while three bishop saints and one male saint are located on the southern wall. The vault of the sanctuary has an image of the Ascension of Christ. The nave of the church is decorated with scenes from the Christological Cycle including the Baptism of Christ, the Transfiguration, the Raising of Lazarus, and the Entry into Jerusalem. The gallery of saints along the southern wall has four unidentified male saints while the northern wall's gallery of saints includes three unidentified saints and St. Constantine and Helena. The Koimesis (the Dormition of the Virgin) is painted on the western wall above the archway connecting the nave to the narthex. This archway is then flanked by two hymnographers. St. Peter (south) and St. Paul (north) decorate the interior of the archway. The barrel vault of the narthex along its eastern side holds additional images relating to the Christological cycle including six scenes from the Passion of Christ and scenes from Christ's healing miracles. The western side of the barrel vault shows eighteen scenes from the Life of the Virgin along with scenes of Paradise and the Last Judgment. The southern wall, although badly damaged, shows the Crucifixion, while the northern wall, also badly damaged, shows the Last Judgment. Standing saints, mostly male monastic saints, line the lower part of each wall of the narthex.

Date Range: 1401 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Village of Kapetaniana (Monofatsi), Heraklion, Crete

Region tags: Crete, Greece

The church is located in the village of Kapetaniana, in the province of Monofatsi (Heraklion region) on the island of Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See p. 157–60.
- Source 2: Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. See no. 670.
- Source 3: Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti nell'isola di Creta. 4 vols. Venice: R. Instituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. See Vol. 4, 566, no. 8.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Topographical Context

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Terracing
- Trackway or road-surface

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: A single nave chapel with an attached narthex.

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: It was once part of the now destroyed Monastery of Vathmou (later the Monastery of the Panagia of Kyrie Eleison)

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to the Panagia (the Virgin)

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Other [specify]: According to the dedicatory inscription the church was sponsored by the priest Grigorios Kalamaras.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s).

Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: plaster and stone.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and

inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of the Panagia, Kapetaniana (Monofatsi), Crete, Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. p.157-60

Reference: Church of the Panagia, Kapetaniana (Monofatsi), Crete, Bissinger, Manfred. Kreta. Byzantinische Wandmalerei. Münchener Arbeiten Zur Kunstgeschichte Und Archäologie 4. Munich: Editio Maris, 1995. p.223-34 (no. 198)

Reference: Church of the Panagia, Kapetaniana (Monofatsi), Crete, Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός Κατάλογος Των Τοιχογραφημένων Εκκλησιών Της Κρήτης. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. p.no. 670

Reference: Church of the Panagia, Kapetaniana (Monofatsi), Crete, Gerola, Giuseppe. Monumenti Veneti Nell'isola Di Creta. Venice: R. Istituto Veneto di Scienze, Lettere ed Arti, 1932. p.Vol. 4, 566 (no. 8)